

IMPROVING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS BASED ON CREATIVE APPROACH

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ANNOTATION This article talks about the importance of developing the creativity of pedagogues in preschool educational organizations.

Key words: personal life, self-awareness, citizenship, professional and ethical aspect, behavior, teacher's skill, creative activity, creativity.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most important features of the content of education is the vital self-awareness of a person, which is characterized by recognition of his personal life and activity as a subject of the environment in which he lives. Civic, professional, and moral self-awareness is essential to human development. The educational process will give effective results only if the teacher teaches students to self-educate, that is, to work consciously on themselves. Making students learn self-education methods depends on the teacher's skill and proper organization of educational activities. Students usually imitate the behavior of their loved ones, sometimes their teachers. That is why the teacher should be able to instill trust and love in the heart of the student, relying on his pedagogical skills. Students observe how the teacher behaves in class and in life, how he dresses, behaves, interacts with people. This is also an effective tool for self-education of students and an important way to increase their social status. Under the direct supervision of the teacher, during the education and upbringing process, during recreation, community work, students develop skills in self-education methods, these methods encourage students to take initiative and think independently.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The concept of "creativity" reflects cultural diversity. For Westerners, creativity is generally considered a novelty. They emphasize that creativity is based on unconventionality, curiosity, imagination, sense of humor, and freedom (Murdock, Ganim, 1993; Shternberg, 1985). Easterners, on the other hand, understand creativity as a process of rebirth of goodness (Hui, Sternberg, 2002; Rudovich, Hui, 1997; Rudovich, Yue, 2000). Although Westerners and Easterners have different views on creativity, representatives of both cultures highly value this quality and its possession (Kaufman, Lan, 2012). Many pedagogues-educators believe that they do not have the ability to be creative. This can be justified for two different reasons:

- firstly, most pedagogues-educators cannot adequately explain what the concept of "creativity" really means;
- secondly, they are unaware of what qualities are directly reflected in the basis of creativity.

RESULTS

In order to teach students to think creatively, to form creative thinking in them, first of all, the educator must be a creative, creative person. After all, if he himself does not have the qualities of creativity, then how can a student (student) encourage children to think creatively. It is not necessary for the teacher to be creative and creative or not, but to organize lessons in the spirit of creativity and creativity, to try new ideas in the educational process. In the lessons, the educator moves in the following 4 directions according to the "creativity road map", and the actions in them are considered signs of creativity of educators (Patti Drepreau):

- Demonstrate creative thinking skills;
- To be able to use strategies that encourage students to master academic subjects with interest;
- Innovative approach and creative approach to finding solutions to pedagogical issues;

The creative potential of a teacher is a multi-level process and it is based on the following principles. The priority principles of the teacher's creativity potential are reflected in the bright manifestation of creativity: 2. Individual characteristics of the person and in life activities 3. Achieving individuality 4. Integrity, consistency, systematicity and capacity building 5. Creative orientation and problem-solving character

DISCUSSION

A teacher-educator does not become a creator by himself. His creative ability is formed over a period of time through consistent study and work on himself, and it gradually improves and develops. As with any specialist, the foundation for creativity of future pedagogues is laid in the student years and is consistently developed in the organization of professional activity. It is important that the pedagogue directs himself to creative activity and is able to organize this activity effectively. In organizing creative activities, the teacher should pay special attention to the creation of creative products of a problematic nature. Self-creative activation is not whether or not a person is creative and creative in the full manifestation and development of his capabilities in creative activities, but organizing activities in the spirit of creativity, creativity, new ideas it is necessary to strive to try in the educational process.

Self-creative activation is not whether or not a person is creative and creative in the full manifestation and development of his capabilities in creative activities, but organizing activities in the spirit of creativity, creativity, new ideas it is necessary to strive to try in the educational process. According to the "creativity road map", the classes move in the following 4 directions, and the actions in them are listed as signs of creativity of pedagogues (Patti Drapeau):

- 1) demonstration of creative thinking skills;
- 2) encouraging to study with interest
- being able to use strategies;
- 3) innovative approach and finding solutions to pedagogical issues
- creative approach;

- 4) expected result

CONCLUSION

It is known that among the qualities and characteristics that form certain abilities of a person, some play a leading role, while others play an auxiliary role. Characteristics of a person related to mutual exchange of ideas play a leading role in pedagogical activity. First of all, perceptive, i.e., characteristics related to the field of perception (observability is the most important of them) play a leading role. allows to make a correct assessment of the condition of the class team and, in particular, of the condition in this pedagogical situation. As a component of the characteristics of the teacher's personality related to the exchange of ideas, it is possible to count the readiness to empathize, that is, to understand the mental state of students and feel sorry for them. A necessary condition for this is love for children.

REFERENCES

Shakhnoza M. IMPROVING THE PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FIRST-YEAR CHILDREN IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 05. – C. 121-124.

qizi, M.S.O. 2022. Improving the Pedagogical and Psychological Competence of First-Year Children in Preschool Education. American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research. 3, 10 (Oct. 2022), 262–265.